
Effect of Canva on the Academic Performance of Financial Accounting Students in Iqra College

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ABSTRACT

Despite the growing popularity of digital teaching tools, the academic performance of the students in financial accounting still remains unfavorable. This paper investigate effect of Canva on academic performance of Financial Accounting students in Iqra College senior secondary school Ilorin. Three research questions were raised for the study. The study employed the Solomon Four-Group Experimental Design to control for the effect of pretesting on the outcome variable. purposive sample techniques were used to select all the 16 S.S one financial accounting students. Financial Accounting Achievement Test (FAAT) was used as the instrument set in line with scheme of work and instructional guide on end of the year adjustment. The achievement test was validated by two research experts; the test was twice administered on all S.S one financial accounting students at Ar-Rasheed college with an interval of two weeks. Test-retest reliability was used to obtained coefficient value of 0.83. Four groups of accounting students from Iqra College S.S one was assigned, with four students each in a group as follows; Groups one and two took a pretest before the intervention. Groups one and three were taught using Canva modules, while Groups two and four taught using traditional method. After the intervention period of four weeks, all groups completed a posttest. mean differences and standard deviation were used for research questions. Therefore, the findings shows that the students taught with Canva have mean score of **21.25** with standard deviation **6.35** against students taught with traditional method mean score of **18.75** with standard deviation **6** which indicate high level performance of students taught with Canva.

KEYWORDS: Canva, Financial Accounting, Academic Performance, Iqra College.

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INTRODUCTION

Decline in performance in senior secondary school demand new teaching method techniques for sustainable academic improvement in financial accounting. Financial accounting academic performance refers to the extent to which students demonstrate mastery of principles and practices in recording, classifying, summarizing, and interpreting financial transactions. Academic performance in financial accounting is the level of success students achieve in understanding and applying accounting principles, which is significantly influenced by instructional method and their capabilities to organize and execute tasks. Academic performance is demonstrated in students' ability to improve their test scores and conceptual understanding through instructional methods. Active involvement in teaching fosters deeper comprehension, resulting in higher achievement in financial accounting (Ezenwafor & Anako, 2022).

However, Jibrin, Adam and Dahiru (2020) stated that academic performance in accounting reflects the degree to which students understand and apply complex financial concepts. Uduonyi, Aliyu and Njoku (2021) explained that academic performance in accounting is influenced by the mode of instructional delivery, with synchronous (live) teaching often yielding better students' comprehension and scores than asynchronous or virtual-only methods. Uchenu (2022) asserted that academic performance is the extent to which students excel in financial accounting as influenced by instructions adopted. Olatunji, Gbadamosi and Adeyemi (2024) noted that, in this context, academic performance refers to the level of achievement students attain when taught using the Students Team Achievement Division (STAD) strategy, which enhances engagement and retention. Olatunji, Gbadamosi and Adeyemi (2024) noted that, in this context, academic performance refers to the level of achievement students attain when taught using the Students Team Achievement Division (STAD) strategy, which enhances engagement and retention.

More so, Akamigbo and Eneja (2020) stated that academic performance is influenced by curriculum design, Teacher preparedness, and access to instructional materials. It refers to how well students meet learning objectives as designed in the accounting curriculum. Balogun (2024) noted that academic performance in accounting is the cumulative result of school-related factors such as classroom environment, teacher quality, and instructional planning. Ofem, Akeke and Ameh (2021) explained that academic performance is the academic standing of students as determined by available financial resources, such as textbooks and instructional infrastructure, that support accounting education. Nwaukwa and Okolocha (2020) Found that academic performance is enhanced through interactive learning methods like the Think-Pair-Share strategy, which allows students to reflect, discuss, and apply financial concepts. Osuala (2004) concluded that financial accounting academic performance refers to the extent to which students demonstrate mastery of principles and practices in recording, classifying, summarizing, and interpreting financial transactions as part of the secondary school business subject curriculum. Academic performance in financial accounting is assessed through students' ability to apply accounting principles to real-life financial problems, as measured by continuous assessments, internal exams, and external exams (Federal Ministry of Education, Nigeria 2013). Furthermore, students' performance in financial accounting is further by their competence in applying double-entry principles, preparing financial statements, and solving practical accounting problems under exam conditions (West Africa examination,2018). Isiaq (2024) asserted that academic performance in financial accounting involves the demonstration of cognitive, affective and psychomotor skills in recording, analyzing, and reporting financial transactions, usually measured through tests and project-based tasks. Financial accounting academic performance refers to the demonstrated ability of students to comprehend and apply financial accounting concepts, principles, and tools in line with the national education objectives. Academic performance in accounting at the senior secondary school level poses challenges to the effective implementation of the accounting curriculum in the educational sector. The effectiveness of academic performance in financial accounting depends largely on the instructional methods adopted in teaching and learning, as well as the ability of teachers to incorporate 21st-century instructional strategies. Such practices are crucial in ensuring that students acquire relevant skills for effective performance in the labour market.

All the more, In the age of digital transformation, the ability to visually communicate complex business concepts has become essential. Financial accounting has traditionally relied on textbooks and classroom lectures. However, the increasing demand for practical skills in visual communication and teamwork has made tools like Canva essential in improving how students present ideas, collaborate, and engage with financial accounting concepts (Isiaq, 2024). With more educational institutions incorporating digital platforms, such as Canva, financial accounting students now have the opportunity to enhance their understanding through interactive, visually appealing presentations, reports, and group projects. As digital tools become integral to modern business practice, they are equally important in preparing students for the workforce, where effective communication and collaboration are key. Isiaq (2024) Canva is an online graphic design platform that allows users to create a wide range of visual content, including presentations, posters, infographics, and social media posts, due to its user-friendly interface and vast library of templates.in particular educators, can benefit from Canva's intuitive design features to engage students and create visually appealing educational materials.

However, Canva for Education is a free offering for teachers and students, providing a suite of tools that facilitate the creation of educational materials, student projects, and collaborative learning activities in a visual format. Canva democratizes design by providing an intuitive, simplified platform for creating professional-looking designs without requiring extensive design experience or expertise (Ingersoll, 2013). Canva serves as an easy-to-use graphic design tool that allows anyone, regardless of their design background, to create high-quality visual content for various media (Forbes, 2020). Canva offers small businesses an affordable and accessible tool for creating high-quality marketing materials such as logos, brochures, and social media content, helping companies enhance their visual branding without the need for professional designers (Chai, 2021).

Also, Canva is a cloud-based platform that allows users to access their designs from anywhere, collaborate with others in real time, and store their creative work online. One of Canva's most important features is its real-time collaboration tool, which allows multiple users to work together on the same design simultaneously, making it a powerful tool for teams and organizations (TechRadar, 2020). Canva is a favorite tool among social media marketers, as it allows for the rapid creation of tailored graphics for social media platforms, enhancing the visual appeal and engagement of online campaigns (Fleming, 2021).

Additionally, Canva operates on a freemium model, where basic design features are free, but users can access premium content such as exclusive templates and advanced features through a subscription to Canva Pro. Canva is all-in-one platform for visual content creation, offering tools for designing presentations, marketing assets, and even video editing, empowering users to craft compelling content quickly (Black & Wiliam, 2018). In educational settings, Canva is used by educators and students to create visually engaging lesson plans, interactive presentations, and classroom posters that enhance the learning experience (Fleming, 2021).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Effect of Canva on the Academic Performance of Financial Accounting Students in Iqra College

Academic performance in financial accounting at Iqra College senior secondary school Ilorin has shown variability, with some students struggling to grasp complex accounting concepts through traditional teaching methods. Despite the growing popularity of digital teaching tools, the academic performance of the students still remains unfavorable. Which calls for emergency intervention to find the possible solution to the problem.

If this problem is not address, there will be continuous problem in academic performance of financial accounting students which we later result in students loose of interest, low enrollment of students in study financial accounting, low labour intensive in financial accounting, low economic planner and low favorable balance of payment, low economic growth and low economic development. However, many researches have been carried out in solving the problem of financial accounting academic performance in senior secondary schools, but to the best knowledge of the researcher non-have been carried out on effect of Canva on the financial accounting academic performance in senior secondary schools in Ilorin. Hence, this study seeks to address this gap by examining the effect of Canva on students' academic performance in financial accounting in Iqra college senior secondary school Ilorin.

Research Questions

1. What is the effect of pretest on the academic performance of accounting students using Canva in Iqra College Ilorin?
2. What is the effect of Canva on the academic performance of accounting students without pretest in Iqra College Ilorin?
3. What is the posttest effect of Canva on the academic performance of financial accounting students in Iqra College Ilorin?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed the Solomon four-group experimental research design to control for the effect of pretesting on the outcome variables. According to Solomon (1949), the four-group design helps control for pretest sensitization effects that may confound the assessment of treatment Canva. This design is widely recognized for its ability to enhance internal validity by separating the effects of pretesting and treatment.

Four groups of accounting students from Iqra College senior secondary (S.S one) were assigned with four students each in a group as follows;

- G₁, G₂ ---- Pretest
- G₁, G₃----- Experimental
- G₂ , G₄----- Control
- G_{1,2,3,4} ----- ----Posttest

Group one and two took a pretest before the intervention. Groups one and three were taught using Canva modules, while Groups two and four taught using traditional method. After the intervention period of four weeks, G_{1,2,3,4} completed a posttest.

The target population of the study comprise all 36 financial accounting students in Iqra college, this population is small because the total number of students taking financial accounting comprises of (S.S one - three) in Iqra college have low enrolment, purposive sample techniques was used to select all 16 seniors secondary (SS one) of financial accounting students for unique instructional guide and scheme. Financial Accounting Achievement Test (FAAT) was used as the instrument set in line with scheme of work and instruction guide. The instrument was validated by two research experts from the department of business education and one expert from test and measurement Al hikmah university. The instrument was twice administered on all S.S one financial accounting students at Ar Rasheed college, okefoma with interval of two weeks as recommended by Uzoagulu (2011) in Affiss (2023). Test-retest was used to obtain the reliability coefficient value of 0.83. pre-treatment phase, a week to the commencement of the treatment session, after the researcher sought the permission of the school management, the researcher groups the S.S one financial accounting students into four with four students each in a group and administered pretest to group one and two. Treatment phase, the teacher taught group one and three using Canva and group two and four using traditional methods which lasted for four weeks with use of instructional guide. Post treatment phase, a week after the treatment phase the researcher administered posttest achievement test to all the four groups. Descriptive statistic of mean, mean differences and standard deviation were used to answer research questions.

RESULT

Research question one: What is the effect of pretest on the academic performance of accounting students using Canva in Iqra College Ilorin?

Table 1: mean and standard deviation on the effect of pretest on the academic performance of accounting students using Canva

Source	n	Pretest	Posttest	Mean differences	Standard deviation
Canva Group 1	4	12.25	21.25	9	6.35
Traditional Group 2	4	11.75	18.75	7	6
Total	8	24	40	16	12.35

Effect of Canva on the Academic Performance of Financial Accounting Students in Iqra College

From Table 1, The table shows the pretest and posttest mean score of students' performance in accounting using Canva with mean differences **9** against **7**. The posttest means of the students indicated students benefit when using Canva in teaching financial accounting. The students taught with Canva have mean score of **21.25** with standard deviation **6.35** against students taught with traditional method **18.75** standard deviation **6** which indicate high level performance of students taught with Canva. Pretest has effect on the academic performance of financial accounting students using Canva.

Research Question 2: What is the effect of Canva on the academic performance of accounting students without pretest in Iqra College Ilorin?

Table 2: mean and standard deviation on effects of Canva on the academic performance of accounting students without pretest

Source	n	Mean	Standard deviation
Canva Group 3	4	20.25	.500
Traditional Group 4	4	17.50	5.00
Grand total	8	37.75	5.5

From Table 2, The table as also show the posttest mean score of students' performance in accounting using Canva without pretest with mean score of **20.25** with standard deviation **.500** against Traditional mean score **17.50** with standard deviation **5.00**. The posttest means of the students indicated students benefit when using Canva in teaching financial accounting without pretest.

Research question 3: What is the posttest effect of Canva on the academic performance of financial accounting students in Iqra College Ilorin?

Table 3: mean and standard deviation on posttest effects of Canva on the academic performance of accounting students

Source	n	Mean	Standard deviation
Canva group 1	4	20.25	.500
Group 3	4	21.25	2.500
Total	8	41.5	3
Traditional Group 2	4	17.50	5.00
Group 4	4	18.75	2.500
Total	8	36.25	7.5
Grand total	16	77.75	10.5

From Table 2, The table also shows the posttest mean score of students' performance in accounting using Canva with mean **41.5** with standard deviation **3** against Traditional mean score **36.25** with standard deviation **7.5**. The posttest means of the students indicated students benefit when using Canva in teaching financial accounting with or without pretest.

DISCUSSION

The findings of the research question one in table 1 revealed that the pretest on the academic performance of accounting students using Canva benefited the students. The finding corroborates with the earlier findings of Adeyemo (2021) who asserted that students taught with pretest have high performance in posttest.

The findings of the research question two in Table 2 reveal that the posttest means of the students indicated students benefit when using Canva in teaching financial accounting without pretest. The findings corroborate with that of Freeman (2020) those students taught without pretest using learning management teaching techniques achieved higher in their posttest score than those taught with conventional.

The findings of research question three in Table 3 reveal that the posttest means of the students indicated that students benefit when using Canva in teaching financial accounting with or without pretest. This finding is supported by Afiss (2023) that students taught with posttest using reciprocal teaching techniques achieved higher ion their posttest score than those taught with conventional.

CONCLUSION

It was concluded that effect of Canva on the academic performance of financial accounting benefited students in Iqra college. That is, students' academic performance improved when using Canva against traditional methods with or without putting pretest into consideration. Therefore, the financial accounting curriculum should lay more emphasis on the uses of Canva for effective instructions in teaching and learning financial accounting in secondary school. Also, financial accounting teachers should be engaged with seminars and workshops on the uses of Canva in effective teaching of financial accounting and also put into

consideration pretest and posttest of instructions for adequate and effective performance in financial accounting. This study demonstrates that Canva significantly improves the academic performance of financial accounting students at Iqra College, independent of pretest effects. By adopting such innovative tools, educational institutions can foster deeper learning and better academic results.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Integrate Canva into the financial Accounting Curriculum; Educators should adopt Canva based teaching modules to enhance students' engagement and understanding.
2. Training should be provided for teacher on effective using of Canva to create instructional materials.
3. The researchers should conduct longitudinal studies to assess the long-term effects of Canva use on academic performance.

REFERENCES

- 1) Adeyemo, S. A. (2011). The relationship between students' participation in school-based extracurricular activities and their achievement in physics. *International Journal of Educational Research and Technology*, 2(1), 35–39.
- 2) Affiss A. A (2023). Effect of Collaborative Mobile Learning Techniques on Academic Performance of students in Office Practice. Kwara state University, malete, School of Postgraduate Studies.
- 3) Becher, T., & Trowler, P. (2022). *Academic Tribes and Territories: Intellectual Enquiry and the Culture of Disciplines*. Open University Press.
- 4) Black, P., & Wiliam, D. (2018). Assessment and Classroom Learning. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 5(1), 7-74.
- 5) Bonwell, C. C., & Eison, J. A. (2021). *Active Learning: Creating Excitement in the Classroom*. ASHE-ERIC Higher Education Report No. 1.
- 6) Chai, C. S. (2010). Technology Integration in Education: A Critical Review of the Literature. *Educational Media International*, 47(2), 109-124.
- 7) Freeman, S. (2020). Active Learning Increases Student Performance in Science, Engineering, and Mathematics. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 111(23), 8410-8415.
- 8) Fleming, N. D. (2021). Teaching and Learning Styles: VARK Strategies. *International Journal of Self-directed Learning*, 6(2), 1-14.
- 9) Garcia-Serrano, C. (2020). The Role of Visuals in Learning: Implications for Classroom Teaching. *Journal of Educational Technology & Society*, 23(3), 20-30.
- 10) Hattie, J., & Timperley, H. (2017). The Power of Feedback. *Review of Educational Research*, 77(1), 81-112.
- 11) Ingersoll, R. M. (2013). Is There Really a Teacher Shortage? Consortium for Policy Research in Education.
- 12) Isiaq J.O (2023) Teacher Perception on Effective Instructional Methods. *FUOYE Journal of Management, Innovation and Entrepreneurship* 2(2)
- 13) Isiaq J.O (2024) Determining Effectiveness of Business Education Curriculum Through Students Perception on Entrepreneurship Skill Acquisition. *KWASU International Journal of Education*,7(1)
- 14) Johnson, D. W., & Johnson, R. T. (2019). An Educational Psychology Success Story: Social Interdependence Theory and Cooperative Learning. *Educational Researcher*, 38(5), 365-379.
- 15) King, A. (2025). Enhancing Peer Interaction and Learning in the Classroom through Cooperative Learning. *Journal of Technology Education*, 7(1), 1-17.
- 16) Lage, M. J., Platt, G. J., & Treglia, M. (2020). Inverting the Classroom: A Gateway to Creating an Inclusive Learning Environment. *The Journal of Economic Education*, 31(1), 30-43.
- 17) Mayer, R. E. (2009). *Multimedia Learning* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- 18) Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council. (2007). *Senior Secondary School Curriculum: Financial Accounting*.
- 19) Nistor, N., & Kopp, M. (2020). The Impact of Educators' Digital Competence on Student Learning Outcomes: The Role of Visual Learning Tools. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 68(2), 337-351.
- 20) Solomon, R. L. (1949). An extension of control group design. *Psychological Bulletin*, 46(2), 137–150. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0058782>
- 21) West African Examinations Council (2018). *Chief Examiners' Report on Financial Accounting*.